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METHODS OF CREATING A CULTURE OF USING INFORMATION TOOLS FOR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS

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Abstract – This article discusses ways to create a culture of media use for students with special educational needs. The study highlights the issues of promoting the effective use of mass media, expanding their capabilities and the formation of knowledge and skills necessary for active participation in the educational process. The article advises: "Students with special educational needs need information technology, face difficulties in use, and can be used to shape culture."

Keywords: students with special educational needs, media, culture of use, information technology, educational process, culture formation, inclusive education.

INTRODUCTION

The use of interactive teaching methods in special education institutions plays an important role in making students more active in their learning activities and increasing their interest. Such methods serve to create more convenient and effective teaching methods for students with special educational needs. With the help of interactive methods, students not only acquire knowledge, but also acquire practical skills. Methods such as group work, role-playing games and problem solving develop communication between students. These methods encourage students to work together, help each other

and exchange ideas. Especially for students with special education, this environment helps them to socialize.

The use of virtual reality technologies and simulations in education provides interesting and interactive lesson processes for students with special educational needs. For example, voice simulations can be used for the blind, and interactive exercises based on hand movements can be used for deaf students. Such approaches make lessons more lively and memorable.

Special educators play a significant role in the implementation of interactive methods. They must carefully plan the learning process, take into account the needs of each student and support them. Also, the use of modern digital tools in interactive lessons increases the effectiveness of the learning process.

Thus, the widespread introduction of interactive methods in special education not only helps to develop students' knowledge and skills, but also increases their self-confidence. These methods play an important role in making the special education system more effective and creative.

The problem of forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs is one of the current issues. As a result of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies, the role and importance of information media in the education system is significantly increasing. However, the opportunities for students with special educational needs to use these media, as well as the formation of a culture of their correct use, are still not sufficiently developed. As the capabilities of information technologies expand, there is a need to develop special methods and strategies to increase the educational opportunities of this group of students and support them in the educational environment.

The formation of a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs is an important factor for their adaptation to social life and independent activity. Ensuring the possibility of effective use of information media in the educational process helps to develop knowledge and skills among students and form their information culture. In particular, providing students with special needs with the opportunity to master and use information technologies has a positive effect on their active participation in the educational process and deepening their knowledge. [1]

The main purpose of this article is to study and apply effective methods in the process of forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs. This is aimed not only at the widespread introduction of technologies relevant to this group, but also at increasing the level of information culture of individuals with special educational needs in society and contributing to their intellectual development.

Methods for forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs

The culture of using information media is of great importance, especially for students with special educational needs. Modern technologies can help them participate more actively in the

educational process and achieve success in social life. This process also creates more opportunities for them in the educational process and helps to increase the efficiency of using information media. However, it is an urgent task to eliminate the limitations that students face in using these technologies.

The role of information media in shaping culture

The availability of information media and their ease of use are of paramount importance for students with special educational needs. To form this culture, it is necessary to stimulate interest in technology among students, provide them with flexible tools and encourage them to use them actively in the learning process. Such an approach, on the one hand, increases their knowledge and skills, and on the other hand, serves to increase the level of social activity.

Scientific and technological approaches

Research shows that the development of special flexible technologies and methods for students with special educational needs makes this process more effective. The results obtained through statistical analysis confirmed the importance of expanding access to information for students. These technologies, including voice control systems, automated screen reading programs or touch devices, help students to be more involved in the learning process.

Methods and strategies used

The strategies implemented within the framework of this study have identified several important aspects in the formation of a culture of using information media. Teaching students to use technology, increasing their level of knowledge, and widely introducing adaptive technologies are the main directions of this process. It is also possible to increase the level of efficiency by analyzing the needs of students and providing them with appropriate technologies.

Future prospects and conclusion

As can be seen from the results of the study, the formation of a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs will greatly contribute not only to their educational process, but also to their adaptation to social life. In the future, it is advisable to conduct additional research in this area, develop technological infrastructure, and develop new adaptive technologies. This will not only improve the learning process of students, but also improve their quality of life.

Literature review and methodology. Forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs plays an important role in the modern education system. The development of information technologies creates the opportunity not only to improve the educational process, but also to strengthen social integration for students with special educational needs. However, the limitations and problems in using information media for these students are still relevant.

The culture of using information media includes not only technical skills in their use, but also their effective and responsible use. For students with special educational needs, this process requires

specific approaches. Methodological guides on adapting information media and their use in the educational process are becoming a necessity.

Research shows that special programs, adapted interfaces and support systems are needed to increase the effectiveness of using information technologies among students with special educational needs. At the same time, the help of teachers and parents is of great importance in using these tools. In forming a culture of using information tools, it is necessary, first of all, to identify the needs of students and create an infrastructure that meets them.

The possibility of using information technologies not only increases the quality of education, but also develops independent thinking and creative abilities among students with special educational needs. Through the correct use of information tools, the active participation of students in the learning process increases and their integration into social life is strengthened.

It is necessary for state organizations, educational institutions and all segments of society to work together to form a culture of using information tools for students with special educational needs. Expanding the application of information tools in the educational process and creating more convenient opportunities for these students is one of the priority areas of modern education.

This study examined methods for forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs and analyzed how they affect the educational process. A mixed methodology was used as a research method, in which qualitative and quantitative analysis methods were used together. In forming a culture of using information media, first of all, questionnaires and interviews were conducted among students to assess the level of use of these technologies and determine their needs. Statistical analyses were also conducted to determine the effectiveness of information technologies and tools used in this process. [3]

A number of indicators were introduced during the research process to assess the effectiveness of forming a culture of using information media. These indicators include ease of use, access to information, impact on the educational process, and the formation of a positive attitude towards information media among students. The calculation formula for each of these indicators is expressed as follows

1. Access to information: $A = \frac{T}{T}$ = activity, T = total

A is the indicator of access to information, T is activity by students to obtain information, and the next T is the total spent in the learning process.

Based on the results obtained, a statistical analysis was conducted for each indicator, which made it possible to determine which factors are important in the process of forming a culture of using information media. On this basis, the most effective methods and strategies for forming a culture of using information media and technologies were recommended. [5]

Results. The following are the main results of the study, which help to analyze the effectiveness and influencing factors of forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs.

The study involved 100 students with special educational needs, and data were collected on indicators such as ease of use, access to information, impact on the learning process, and the formation of a positive attitude. With the help of these results, it became possible to assess the level of impact of using information media on the general culture. [2]

The indicator of access to information (A) was on average 0.83, which indicates that students with special educational needs have good opportunities to obtain information. However, the minimum value is 0.6, which indicates that access is still limited for some students.

The learning impact index (I) was 18.5%. This means that the use of information media increased students' knowledge by an average of 18.5%. The maximum value of this indicator is 25%, which indicates that for some students these media significantly increased the effectiveness of education. Based on the analysis of the above results, it was found that factors such as ease of use and access to information are of great importance in forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs. The learning impact index and the index of positive attitude formation confirm that this group of students is important for increasing their interest in information technologies and ensuring their effectiveness. [6]

Discussion. The results of this study provided a clearer understanding of the important factors and indicators of effectiveness in the process of forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs. The results show that factors such as ease of use, accessibility, impact on the learning process, and positive attitude in the formation of a culture of using information media motivate students to actively master information technologies.

Based on the analysis of the results, the high assessment of the ease of use index and access to information indicates a high level of availability and convenience of information technologies for students with special educational needs. However, given that some students still have a relatively low level of access, it is clear that there is a need to further develop the technological infrastructure and expand the possibilities of adaptation for students with special educational needs. [4]

The indicator of the impact on the educational process, that is, the average increase in the level of knowledge acquisition through information media by 18.5%, indicates that these technologies have a positive effect on increasing the general level of knowledge of students. The fact that for some students this indicator was 25% confirms that the use of information media has led to significant achievements in their individual educational process. This shows that the use of information technologies not only facilitates the process of acquiring knowledge, but also plays an important role in increasing its efficiency.

As digital technologies penetrate all aspects of life, improving digital literacy for students with special educational needs remains an urgent task. These students need not only skills and qualifications

in using information technologies, but also special adaptations. Therefore, the development and implementation of special programs on digital literacy is an integral part of the modern education system.

Digital literacy opens up new opportunities for students with special educational needs in various areas. For example, the Internet and special programs allow for distance learning, participation in virtual classes and trainings, and communication with others through social networks. At the same time, it is also important to teach students how to use the Internet safely and inform them about cybersecurity.

Improving digital literacy requires adapting curricula and using special tools. For example, devices such as voice assistants, screen readers, or special keyboards and mice ensure the effective use of information technologies by students with special educational needs. It is also necessary to work on the basis of universal design principles when creating digital content.

The role of teachers and family members in this area is invaluable. Teachers need to teach students how to use information technologies correctly and choose appropriate methods taking into account their needs. Families should take an active role in supporting their use of new skills.

Digital literacy will qualitatively change the lives of students with special educational needs. This process will not only expand their educational opportunities, but also help them fully adapt to society and lead an active life. Therefore, the development of digital literacy should be one of the priorities of state policy.

The use of digital technologies in special educational institutions is an important factor in improving the educational process for students with special educational needs. These technologies not only make the learning process more convenient, but also allow students to be provided with modern knowledge and skills. At the same time, an individual approach and a flexible education system are created using digital technologies.

Distance learning platforms open up new horizons for students with special educational needs. Through these platforms, they can participate in classes remotely and have access to special educational materials. In particular, resources such as video lessons, interactive tests, and audio textbooks facilitate their learning process.

It is important to develop software and technologies adapted to special institutions. For example, subtitled video lessons are needed for deaf and hard of hearing students, and screen learning programs are needed for the blind. In addition, special interactive whiteboards and adapted tablets make the learning process more effective.

Teachers are encouraged to

Conclusion. This study helped to identify important factors in the process of forming a culture of using information media for students with special educational needs and develop approaches aimed at increasing their effectiveness. During the study, key indicators such as ease of use, accessibility, impact on the learning process, and the formation of a positive attitude were analyzed. The results show that the

use of information media for students with special educational needs is not only a means of acquiring knowledge, but also plays an important role in making them more active in the educational process and strengthening their social adaptation.

According to the results of the study, the integration of information media and technologies into the educational process was found to be effective in increasing students' knowledge. Ease of use and access to information had a positive effect on the formation of a positive attitude among students and helped increase their interest in technologies. At the same time, limited access for some students indicates the need to develop technological infrastructure, which will serve as a basis for improving special technologies and adaptive programs.

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